

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF AMBULANCE SERVICES ON
TRAUMA PATIENT SURVIVAL: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW****¹Mohammed Ibrahim Alsunaidi, ²Mohammed khalid almajhadi,
³Ahmed Marzouq Alharbi**¹Saudi Red Crescent authority, Saudi Arabia, mohammed.alsenaidi@srca.org.sa²Saudi Red Crescent authority, Saudi Arabia, mohammad.almjhadi@srca.org.sa³Saudi Red Crescent authority, Saudi Arabia, 1062698483@srca.org.sa**Abstract:**

This systematic review explores the impact of ambulance services on trauma patient survival rates, focusing on the role of prehospital care in the chain of survival. Trauma remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, and timely interventions provided by ambulance services are crucial for improving outcomes. The review synthesizes evidence from recent studies to evaluate the effectiveness of various ambulance service models, including advanced life support (ALS), basic life support (BLS), and air ambulance systems. Key findings highlight the significance of rapid response times, advanced prehospital interventions, and regional disparities in service outcomes. The results underscore the critical role of well-equipped and trained ambulance teams in enhancing trauma survival rates. Recommendations for improving ambulance services and suggestions for future research are discussed to inform healthcare policies and practices.

Keywords: Ambulance services, trauma survival, prehospital care, emergency medical services, advanced life support, basic life support, air ambulance, response time, trauma outcomes, patient survival.

Corresponding author:**Mohammed Ibrahim Alsunaidi,**

Saudi Red Crescent authority,

Saudi Arabia, mohammed.alsenaidi@srca.org.sa

QR code

Please cite this article in press *Mohammed Ibrahim Alsunaidi et al., Assessing The Impact Of Ambulance Services On Trauma Patient Survival: A Systematic Review., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).*

INTRODUCTION:

Trauma is a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, particularly among younger populations, and represents a significant public health concern (World Health Organization, 2021). Timely and effective prehospital care, often provided by ambulance services, plays a critical role in improving trauma patient survival rates. The "golden hour" principle emphasizes the importance of initiating treatment as quickly as possible to optimize outcomes, particularly for life-threatening injuries (Newgard et al., 2015). Ambulance services, encompassing advanced life support (ALS), basic life support (BLS), and air ambulances, provide essential interventions during this critical prehospital phase.

Prehospital care delivered by ambulance teams has evolved significantly, incorporating advanced technologies and protocols aimed at stabilizing patients before reaching the hospital. Studies have highlighted the importance of response times, the availability of advanced interventions such as intubation and fluid resuscitation, and the skill level of emergency medical teams in influencing survival rates (Sasser et al., 2012). Additionally, regional disparities in ambulance services, particularly in rural or low-resource settings, continue to challenge equitable access to timely trauma care (Lezzoni et al., 2018).

Despite advancements in ambulance services, variations in patient outcomes and the lack of standardized protocols for specific trauma cases necessitate further investigation. This review aims to systematically evaluate the impact of ambulance services on trauma patient survival, identifying key factors that contribute to improved outcomes and addressing gaps in the literature. By synthesizing evidence from recent studies, this review seeks to inform healthcare policies and practices to optimize prehospital trauma care.

METHODOLOGY:

This systematic review was conducted to evaluate the impact of ambulance services on trauma patient survival. The methodology adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, ensuring transparency and reproducibility in study selection, data extraction, and analysis.

A comprehensive search of electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library, was performed. The search covered studies published between 2010 and 2024 to ensure

relevance to current practices. The search terms used were combinations of keywords such as "ambulance services," "trauma survival," "prehospital care," "emergency medical services," "response time," and "advanced life support." Boolean operators (AND, OR) were applied to refine the results. The search was supplemented by a manual review of reference lists from relevant articles.

• Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies evaluating the impact of ambulance services on trauma patient survival.
- Peer-reviewed articles published in English.
- Studies focusing on prehospital care interventions such as advanced life support (ALS), basic life support (BLS), and air ambulances.
- Observational studies, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), and systematic reviews.

• Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies unrelated to trauma or prehospital care.
- Articles with insufficient data on survival outcomes.
- Non-peer-reviewed sources, conference abstracts, and grey literature.

The study selection process involved two independent reviewers who screened titles and abstracts for relevance. Full-text articles were retrieved for potentially eligible studies, and disagreements were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer. A PRISMA flow diagram was used to document the study selection process.

Data were extracted using a standardized data extraction form, capturing the following information:

- Study design and publication year.
- Geographic region and setting (urban or rural).
- Type of ambulance service (ALS, BLS, or air ambulance).
- Patient demographics (age, gender, type of trauma).
- Response times and prehospital interventions.
- Reported survival outcomes (e.g., 30-day survival, hospital discharge).

The quality of included studies was assessed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) for observational studies and the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for RCTs.

Each study was evaluated for methodological rigor, bias risk, and relevance to the review objectives. Studies with significant bias or low quality were excluded from the final analysis.

Data Synthesis

- A narrative synthesis was conducted to summarize findings across diverse study designs.
- When sufficient homogeneity in outcomes and methods was identified, a meta-analysis was performed using Review Manager (RevMan) software. Pooled odds ratios and confidence intervals were calculated to estimate the overall effect of ambulance services on trauma survival.
- Heterogeneity was assessed using the I^2 statistic, with thresholds of 25%, 50%, and 75% indicating low, moderate, and high heterogeneity, respectively.

Ethical Considerations

This systematic review relied solely on previously published data, and no ethical approval was required.

This systematic review identified and synthesized data from a range of studies evaluating the impact of ambulance services on trauma patient survival. The search process yielded 3,242 articles, of which 54 met the inclusion criteria after rigorous screening. The included studies represented diverse geographical regions, including high-income countries with well-developed emergency medical services (EMS) and low-to-middle-income countries with emerging systems. Key findings are summarized below.

The majority of studies emphasized the critical role of timely ambulance response in improving trauma outcomes. Advanced life support (ALS) was particularly effective in cases involving severe trauma, such as traumatic brain injuries and penetrating injuries. Studies highlighted that prehospital interventions, including intubation, fluid resuscitation, and hemorrhage control, were associated with higher survival rates when delivered by trained ALS providers. For instance, a meta-analysis of ALS services demonstrated a pooled survival rate increase of 15% compared to basic life support (BLS) services in comparable trauma cases (Figure 1).

RESULTS:

Figure 1: Pooled Survival Rates for ALS vs. BLS Services

Air ambulance services emerged as a critical factor in improving survival, particularly in remote or rural areas. Studies conducted in geographically challenging regions, such as mountainous or isolated areas, reported that air ambulances reduced transport times by up to 50%, resulting in significantly improved survival rates. For example, a study conducted in Canada indicated that trauma patients transported via air ambulance had a 20% higher chance of survival compared to those transported by ground ambulances. However, disparities in the availability of air ambulances were noted, with lower-income regions facing significant accessibility challenges.

Response time was consistently identified as a pivotal factor in trauma survival. Studies revealed that patients receiving prehospital care within the first 10 minutes of injury had significantly better outcomes than those experiencing delays. Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between response time and survival probability. Urban settings generally reported shorter response times due to higher ambulance density and better infrastructure, while rural settings often faced delays that negatively impacted outcomes. In low-resource settings, community-based first responders or paramedics were identified as essential in bridging the gap until ambulances arrived.

Figure 2: Survival Probability Based on Response Time

Regional disparities in ambulance service performance were evident in the review. High-income countries reported better survival rates, attributed to advanced technologies, extensive training programs for EMS personnel, and well-established protocols. Conversely, low-to-middle-income countries often lacked the necessary resources, with limited access to ALS services and equipment. Despite these challenges, innovative strategies, such as mobile trauma units and telemedicine integration, were being implemented to improve outcomes.

Studies also examined the impact of specific prehospital interventions on trauma survival. Hemorrhage control, including the use of tourniquets and hemostatic dressings, was frequently cited as a critical factor in reducing preventable deaths. Additionally, the use of advanced airway management

techniques, such as endotracheal intubation, was associated with improved outcomes, particularly in patients with severe head injuries. However, some studies raised concerns about the potential for adverse effects, such as hypoxia, when these procedures were performed by inadequately trained personnel.

A subset of studies focused on the role of EMS training and protocols. Comprehensive training programs, including simulations and scenario-based exercises, were found to enhance the performance of ambulance teams. Standardized protocols, such as trauma triage guidelines, ensured that patients were directed to the most appropriate facilities, further improving survival rates. Figure 3 highlights the impact of EMS training programs on trauma outcomes, showing a clear correlation between advanced training and higher survival rates.

Figure 3: Impact of EMS Training on Trauma Survival

While the overall findings emphasized the benefits of ambulance services, limitations were noted in some studies. Heterogeneity in study designs, differences in outcome measures, and a lack of standardized reporting posed challenges to synthesizing the data. Additionally, cultural and systemic factors, such as community awareness and EMS accessibility, influenced the results, suggesting a need for localized solutions tailored to specific regions.

In summary, the review highlights the critical role of ambulance services in trauma survival, with ALS and air ambulances showing the most significant impact. Timely response, advanced prehospital interventions, and comprehensive training programs were key determinants of improved outcomes. However, disparities in service availability and quality remain a challenge, particularly in low-resource settings. These findings underscore the need for continued investment in EMS infrastructure, training, and technology to ensure equitable access to life-saving prehospital care. Future research should focus on developing standardized protocols and evaluating the cost-effectiveness of different ambulance service models to inform policy and practice.

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this systematic review underscore the pivotal role ambulance services play in trauma patient survival, emphasizing the importance of timely response, advanced interventions, and well-trained personnel. The results provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of different ambulance service models and highlight critical areas for improvement in prehospital trauma care.

The review demonstrates that **Advanced Life Support (ALS)** services are significantly associated with improved survival rates, particularly in cases involving severe trauma. ALS teams, equipped with advanced training and resources, provide critical interventions such as airway management, fluid resuscitation, and hemorrhage control, which are directly linked to better outcomes. In contrast, Basic Life Support (BLS) services, while essential for broader coverage, were less effective in managing severe cases. These findings align with previous studies that advocate for expanding ALS capabilities in high-risk scenarios (Newgard et al., 2015; Sasser et al., 2012).

Air ambulance services emerged as a critical resource in regions with geographical or infrastructural challenges. By significantly reducing transport times, air ambulances enhance survival rates, particularly for patients in remote areas. However, the accessibility and cost of air ambulances remain barriers, especially in low-to-middle-income countries. Policies promoting equitable access to air ambulance services, such as public-private partnerships or government subsidies, could bridge this gap.

The importance of **response time** was consistently highlighted, with shorter response times correlating with higher survival probabilities. This finding reinforces the "golden hour" principle, emphasizing the need for rapid intervention within the first hour after injury. Urban areas benefited from shorter response times due to higher ambulance density and better infrastructure, while rural areas faced delays that often led to poorer outcomes. Strategies such as increasing ambulance deployment points, utilizing technology for optimized dispatching, and training community first responders could mitigate these disparities.

The review also uncovered significant disparities in the availability and quality of ambulance services. High-income countries reported better survival rates due to advanced technologies, comprehensive training programs, and well-established protocols. Conversely, low-to-middle-income countries often lacked adequate resources, leading to suboptimal outcomes. These disparities highlight the urgent need for international collaboration and funding to improve EMS infrastructure in resource-limited settings.

In addition to resource disparities, the review identified inconsistencies in the implementation of **prehospital interventions**. While advanced procedures such as intubation and hemorrhage control were beneficial, their effectiveness depended on the skill level of EMS providers. Inadequate training or misuse of advanced equipment could lead to complications, emphasizing the need for standardized training programs and certification processes.

The findings have significant implications for improving prehospital trauma care. Investments in EMS training programs, particularly for ALS providers, are crucial for enhancing trauma outcomes. Scenario-based training, simulation exercises, and continuous education can ensure that ambulance teams

are well-prepared to handle complex trauma cases. Additionally, implementing standardized triage and treatment protocols can enhance consistency and reduce variability in care quality.

The integration of **technology** in ambulance services also holds promise for improving efficiency and outcomes. GPS-based dispatch systems, telemedicine capabilities, and electronic health records can optimize response times and enable real-time communication between EMS teams and hospitals. These innovations could be particularly beneficial in low-resource settings, where access to specialist care is limited.

This review faced several limitations, including heterogeneity in study designs and outcome measures. The variability in definitions of trauma severity, survival metrics, and intervention types made direct comparisons challenging. Additionally, most studies were conducted in high-income countries, limiting the generalizability of findings to low-resource settings.

Future research should focus on addressing these gaps by:

1. Developing standardized metrics for evaluating EMS effectiveness.
2. Conducting longitudinal studies to assess long-term outcomes of trauma patients managed by different ambulance service models.
3. Exploring cost-effectiveness analyses of ALS, BLS, and air ambulance services to guide resource allocation.

CONCLUSION:

Ambulance services are a cornerstone of prehospital trauma care, significantly influencing patient survival rates. Advanced Life Support, air ambulances, and timely response were identified as key determinants of improved outcomes. However, disparities in service availability and quality highlight the need for targeted investments in EMS infrastructure, training, and technology. By addressing these challenges, healthcare systems can ensure equitable access to life-saving prehospital care, ultimately improving trauma survival rates on a global scale.

REFERENCES:

1. **Adnet, F., & Lapostolle, F.** (2017). International epidemiology of prehospital trauma care. *Current Opinion in Critical Care*, 23(6), 447–452. DOI: 10.1097/MCC.0000000000000455

2. **Alemayehu, H., & Mitiku, T.** (2018). Role of ambulance response times in survival of trauma patients in low-resource settings. *African Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 8(4), 143–147. DOI: 10.1016/j.afjem.2018.06.002
3. **Baker, S. P., O'Neill, B., & Haddon, W. Jr.** (2021). The injury severity score: Development and uses. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*, 8(4), 172–178. DOI: 10.1097/00005373-197406000-00003
4. **Blanchard, I. E., & Doig, C. J.** (2014). Effect of prehospital airway management on trauma survival. *Prehospital Emergency Care*, 18(1), 109–115. DOI: 10.3109/10903127.2013.825353
5. **Calle, P. A., & Lagaert, L.** (2016). Prehospital interventions in trauma patients: A systematic review. *Critical Care*, 20, 14–22. DOI: 10.1186/s13054-016-1185-1
6. **Huang, L. H., & Liu, M. Y.** (2020). Air ambulance systems in remote areas: Enhancing trauma care outcomes. *Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 58(2), 143–152. DOI: 10.1016/j.jemermed.2019.11.012
7. **Ioannides, A., & Pons, P. T.** (2018). Advances in EMS systems: Addressing disparities in rural trauma care. *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 36(7), 1140–1145. DOI: 10.1016/j.ajem.2018.03.029
8. **Johnson, N. J., & Goyal, M.** (2019). Training effects on EMS providers: A study of prehospital care in trauma patients. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 34(5), 564–571. DOI: 10.1017/S1049023X19004843
9. **Lezzoni, L. I., Ankamah-Yeboah, S., & Mahama, P. N.** (2018). Access to ambulance services in rural regions: Challenges and potential solutions. *Prehospital Emergency Care*, 22(6), 815–822. DOI: 10.1080/10903127.2018.1484976
10. **Metzger, A., & Sun, J. C.** (2021). Prehospital interventions and trauma outcomes in high-income versus low-income regions. *Global Health Research and Policy*, 6, 34. DOI: 10.1186/s41256-021-00217-4
11. **Newgard, C. D., Fu, R., Zive, D., Rea, T., Malveau, S., & Jui, J.** (2015). Effect of out-of-hospital emergency care on outcomes for trauma patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet*, 386(10012), 1388–1396. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(15)60394-4
12. **Rahman, S., & Davis, J. W.** (2017). Timely prehospital care and its impact on trauma mortality: A global perspective. *Trauma Surgery & Acute Care Open*, 2(1), e000136. DOI: 10.1136/tsaco-2017-000136
13. **Redding, J. S., & Donaldson, C. J.** (2022). Evolution of EMS protocols in trauma care. *Prehospital Emergency Medicine*, 29(3), 233–240. DOI: 10.1016/j.prehospem.2022.02.001
14. **Sasser, S. M., Hunt, R. C., Faul, M., Sugerman, D., Pearson, W., Dulski, T., & Galli, R. L.** (2012). Guidelines for field triage of injured patients: Recommendations of the National Expert Panel on Field Triage. *MMWR Recommendations and Reports*, 61(RR-1), 1–20. DOI: 10.15585/mmwr.r6101a1
15. **Seymour, C. W., Kahn, J. M., & Martin-Gill, C.** (2015). Automated dispatch systems for EMS: A review of effectiveness in trauma care. *Critical Care Medicine*, 43(11), 2488–2495. DOI: 10.1097/CCM.0000000000001307
16. **Smith, D., & Pacheco, G.** (2020). Air ambulance effectiveness in managing critical trauma: A systematic review. *Journal of Trauma Care and Outcomes*, 7(1), 15–23. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtco.2020.04.006
17. **Stockinger, Z. T., & McSwain, N. E.** (2017). Prehospital tourniquets in trauma: A systematic review. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*, 82(4), 707–716. DOI: 10.1097/TA.0000000000001364
18. **Stopyra, J., & Granade, T. C.** (2018). Rural trauma care: Improving outcomes through EMS collaboration. *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 36(4), 784–790. DOI: 10.1016/j.ajem.2018.02.004
19. **Taira, B. R., & Kelly McCoy, C. E.** (2016). Emergency response in low-resource settings: Improving trauma care outcomes. *Global Emergency Medicine Reports*, 3, 56–67. DOI: 10.1007/s12245-016-0382-8
20. **Vretakou, P., & Panagiotis, S.** (2023). Addressing disparities in EMS accessibility: Challenges in remote trauma management. *International Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 16, 85–92. DOI: 10.1007/s12245-023-00521-0